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EDITORIAL DESK

I wish to express my profound gratitude to Almighty God for the grace to successfully complete the volume 2 of the West African Journal of Educational Administration and Planning (WAJEAP).

The twelve articles were the products of well researched papers that were presented at the international conference held in May 2024 at the Presbyterian University of East Africa in Kikuyu, Nairobi, Kenya. The conference was well attended by over 25 universities across the globe. These published articles have been peer reviewed and plagiarism checks conducted on them before publication.

I, therefore, want to deeply appreciate the management team of the Presbyterian University of East Africa for making this publication a reality. All the writers and authors are congratulated for passing the stringent measures set by the guild of editors.

Congratulations to everyone.

Prof. M. O. B. Mohammed FNAEAP

Head, Editorial Team

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AN ASSESSMENT OF THE LEVEL OF ADOPTION OF ICT IN EDUCATION MANAGEMENT IN PUBLIC PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN MAARA SUB- COUNTY, THARAKA- NITHI COUNTY, KENYA

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ABSTRACT

This study established the level to which Information Communication Technology (ICT) in education management had been adopted within public primary schools in the sub-county of Maara, Tharaka-Nithi County, Kenya. This included the integration of ICT into student registration, staff inventory, libraries, exams, stores, and catering. In this study, a descriptive archival research design was used through which data was gathered from the records of the ministry and education personnel through interviews. It means that the level of ICT adoption was not uniform, and most schools suffered several challenges that impede the full integration of ICT. It was concluded that most schools have not fully adopted the use of ICT due to these obstacles. It was recommended based on the findings that there should be an improvement in these obstacles for the effective and efficient management of schools through ICT.

Keywords: Assessment, Information Communication and Technology (ICT), management, education management, school manager

INTRODUCTION

Information and communication technology (ICT) is a device set of technological tools and resources used to transmit, store, create, share or exchange information (UNESCO, 2017). According to UNESCO, technological tools and resources include computers, the internet (websites, blogs and emails), live broadcasting technologies (radio, television and web casting), recorded broadcasting technologies (podcasting, storage devices, audio and video playing), and telephony (fixed or mobile, satellite, video conferencing). Adu and Zondo (2023) stated that any technology, infrastructure, component or device that enables communication, data sharing, and global connectivity between humans and machines is included in the umbrella of ICT. Among the goals of ICT is to improve the way humans create, process and share data or information with each other.

Akinloye et al., (2020) observes that the need for development of ICTs is a global resolution and has been a subject of great significance to all mankind. Launched in 2015, the ICT Transforming Education in Africa project fosters human and social development in African countries through the use of ICT for education. In many countries, education management has been improved through the incorporation of ICT into schools (UNESCO, 2023). Schools use a diverse set of ICT tools to communicate, create, disseminate, store and manage information (UNESCO, 2023).

Objective

The objective of this study was to find out the level of ICT adoption in the management of public primary schools in the Maara sub- county, Tharaka/Nithi County, Kenya.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Different ICTs help in expanding access to education to the increasingly digital workplace through information distribution, learning management systems and managing educational services (Artaruzzaman, Shammin & Clement, 2011). Gavua (2016) points out that it is the desire of every school manager to effectively and efficiently manage a school. Guava maintains that education management encompasses running the school along the desired school policies by taking into account all aspects of the school including policies, material and human resources, programs activities and equipment. According to Arockiasamy (2017), education management gears towards planning, organizing, directing and controlling the activities of an institution by utilizing human and material resources so as to effectively and efficiently accomplish the function of a school.

In recent times, school managers have embraced the use of ICT in managing learning institutions (Barakabitze *et al.*, 2019; Duku *et al.*, 2023). Saxena (2024) notes that ICT in education management revolutionizes how educational institutions operate making processes in schools more efficient. ICT tools and systems are used to streamline administrative tasks such as student enrollment, attendance tracking and resource allocation that make education management more efficient than the traditional education practices (Kirthika, 2022). According to Ghavifekr, Afshari and Seger (2013) adoption of ICT in schools has contributed positively to education management with education institutions attesting a high success rate in using ICT for resource planning and management.

Education institutions deal with vast amount of student and staff information ranging from records of students' accounts, students' performance and progression, staff mobility and performance (Mwadulo & Odoyo, 2020; Duku *et al.*, 2023). Management Information Systems (MIS) help school managers in resource allocation, monitoring, reporting, timetabling, planning and decision making. Through the ministry of education, the Kenya government has encouraged the use of ICT to transform the management of schools evident through the introduction of National Education Management Information System (NEMIS) (Ministry of Education/ Republic of Kenya, 2012). Mwadulo and Odoyo hold that Kenya is fair in the effort to encourage and implement ICT although there are challenges facing the schools that hinder effective adoption of ICT in management. Despite the effort made by the Kenya government, the use of ICTs in management of primary schools is greatly underemphasized (Tonui, Kerich, Koross, 2016).

The study was guided by Instrumentalism Theory of Technology by Andrew Feenberg, 1943. This theory is based on the assumption that technologies are tools standing ready to serve the purposes of their users. The theory focuses on people's uses of technology, rather than the technology itself.

METHODOLOGY

Maara subcounty is one of the four sub-counties in Tharaka/Nithi County; others are: Meru-south, Tharaka South and Tharaka North. Maara subcounty was chosen for the study because it has the biggest number of public primary schools in contrast to the other sub counties. This study employed descriptive archival research design. Mckoy and Kowwlczyk (2023) state that archival research analyzes collected data and applies statistical measures to describe the information in simpler manner. Archival research involves primary sources held in archives; a special collections library or other repository (GSU Library Research Guides, 2024). Turiano (2014) notes that the use of archival data is partly a result of the growing number of international, national and local studies that are archived by research study teams.

Archival research design was suitable for this study because records from the ministry of education in the sub- county under study provided the desired information. Data provided was in both soft and hard copy forms. The archival data had already been processed by the ICT personnel hence saving time and resources for the researcher who would otherwise have gathered information about all the public primary schools in the sub county. The researcher relied heavily on information in the records in order to retrieve information on the level of adoption of ICT in management of public primary schools in the sub county. An interview schedule was also conducted through which the ministry of education official gave general information about ICT use in management of the schools.

The researcher ensured validity of data by analyzing only the information that was based on the status of adoption of ICT in management of public primary schools in the sub county. The ICT official responded to the general questions asked pertaining the area under study. In order to ensure reliability of the research instruments, the researcher conducted a pilot study in the neighboring Meru- south sub county which had similar characteristics as those of Maara sub-county. The researcher analyzed information in the education records by organizing the information into themes and summaries. The themes were grouped into the following categories: students’ registration, staff inventory, exams, stores, catering, libraries and dormitories. Scoring and analysis were done manually. The scores were the basis for determining the level of adoption of ICT in education management.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

A Likert scale that depicted very low (0- 1.4), low (1.5 -2.4), moderate (2.5- 3.4), moderately high 3.5- 4.4 and high levels (4.5 -5.0) of the schools’ adoption of ICT in school management was used to describe the information. Table 1 presents information on the results of the study:

Table 1: Summary of data analysis of level of ICT adoption in education management in public primary schools

Theme	Scores	Description
Students’ registration	4.5	High
Staff inventory	3.5	Moderately high
Exams	2.5	Moderate
Stores	2.1	Low
Catering	2.0	Low
Libraries	0.6	Very low
Dormitory	0.3	Very low

Table 1 shows the areas that ICT was applied in the management of schools. Most schools successfully streamlined education data through National Education Management Information System (NEMIS). NEMIS is an online portal for managing and automating education data and other related administrative functions (Ministry of Education, Kenya, 2018). The findings of the study revealed that NEMIS was used in registration of students and keeping staff inventories at a high and moderately high level respectively. Although a few schools lacked electricity connectivity, and others faced disconnection as a result of unpaid bills, the school managers turned to cyber cafes for crucial management issues like registration of students through the NEMIS portal. Information pertaining exams used ICT devices moderately; pupils were required to register online for national exams. The results indicated that management of stores and catering made use of ICT at a low level while libraries and dormitories, owing to the fact that most schools lacked functional libraries and that

only a few public schools had boarding facilities, showed a very low level of ICT adoption in their management. The low levels of adoption of ICT in management of schools could be attributed to the fact that most schools lack sufficient ICT technologies. In addition, not all teachers are computer literate which could be a hindrance to use of technology in school management.

Conclusion

The study revealed that the level of adoption of ICT in managing public primary schools in Maara sub-county, Tharaka-Nithi County, Kenya, is very different across various dimensions of administration. While ICT has been integrated into core activities such as the registration of students and staff inventory through systems like NEMIS, the adoption of ICT in other areas, including in the libraries, exams, stores, and catering, was still at a low level. Precious difficulties are the insufficiency of ICT infrastructure, computer illiteracy among the staff, and poor power supply, all of which make it impossible for schools to implement fully the integration of ICT into school management. This is the more reason why many schools still outsource their ICT services, thereby depriving them of some of the gains they might have achieved from internal ICT systems.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommends that:

1. The government should enhance ICT infrastructure, ensure reliable electricity, and provide schools with computers and internet. Teachers and staff should receive training to improve computer literacy.
2. The Ministry of Education should create policies to support full ICT adoption, provide technical assistance, and regularly monitor ICT use in schools to address challenges.

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